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COMPARATIVE STUDY OF RATIO ANALYSIS FOR COMPARING THE PERFORMANCE OF TCS & INFOSYS FOR THE YEAR 2010-2014

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Abstract

In the present complex technological world, information Technology (IT) sector has become the integral part & it is the fastest growing sector. "The present study has been planned to compare the performance of TCS & Infosys by making a comparative study of their Ratio Analysis". The study consists variables like current ratio(C.R), debtors turnover ratio(DTR), assets turnover ratio(ATR), interest coverage ratio(ICR), net profit ratio(NPR), debt equity ratio(DER), earning per share(EPS) and dividend per share (DPS)for a period of 5 years from 2010-2014. The study was based on secondary data from records, reports and profile of the organization.

Keywords:- net profit ratio, earning per share, dividend per share, fundamentals, balance sheet, Profit and loss account.

Key words: Current Ratio, Interest Coverage Ratio (ICR), Assets Turnover Ratio (ATR), Dividend Per Share (DPS)

Introduction

An analysis of financial statement with the help of 'ratio' may be termed as 'ratio analysis. It implies the process of computing, determining and presenting the relationship of items as group of items of financial statements.

"The work of interpretation can be made easier by establishing quantitative relationship between the facts given in financial statements."

- Alexander Wall (1909)

Objective of Ratio Analysis

The object of ratio-analysis is to help management in analysing & interpreting the financial statements, to get adequate information useful for the performance of various functions like-planning, co-ordinating control, communication & forecasting etc.

Ratio provides power to speak. The use of ratio-analysis has increased considerably. It is new being used as a device to diagnose the financial health of a business concern. It signifies whether the financial health of the concern is vital, strong, good or poor & weak.

Like doctor’s prescription, ratios represent the figure containing the condensed report of the position, progress & problems of the concern. They facilitate the work or gauging the profitability, solvency & activity of the concern.

Ratio-Analysis may highlight upon the few phases of the business operations in which the outsiders are most interested by ascertaining the rate & direction of change & future potentialities, thus, ratio-analysis is a very powerful tool for both internal & external analysis.

Objective of the Study

- 1) To assess the financial performance of TCS & Infosys.
- 2) To compare the financial position of TCS & Infosys.

Hypothesis:-

- There is no difference between the selected variables of the sample companies.
- There is a significant difference between the selected variables of the sample companies.

Research Methodology

Sample:- The present study is descriptive and analytical in nature. The sample consists of two I.T sector companies i.e..TCS and Infosys.

Key variables:- The variables which have been considered in the study are current ratio, debt equity ratio, asset turnover ratio, debtors turnover ratio, net profit ratio, earning per share, dividend per share, interest coverage ratio.

Time period:- The period of the study is from 2010-2014.

Sources of data:- The data on key variables was compiled from annual reports of the respective companies.

Statistical tools:- The statistical tools that have been used in this study include ratio analysis.

Data analysis and interpretation / Current Ratio

Yr.	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
TCS	1.49	2.45	2.48	2.85	3.18
Infosys	4.28	5.34	4.91	4.75	3.70

Interpretation:- The objective of current ratio is to assess the ability of the enterprise to meet its short-term liabilities promptly. The ideal current ratio is considered if it is 2:1. From the above data it is

clear that the current ratio of TCS tends to increase every year & current ratio of Infosys are declined. But the current ratio of both the company's is more than 2:1 which indicates that the current ratio is too high (more than 2), then the company may not be using its current assets be efficiently this may also indicate problem in working capital management.

But, all other thing being equal, creditor consider a high current ratio to be better than a low current ratio, because a high current ratio mean that the company is more likely to meet its liabilities which are due over the next 12 months.

H:- From the above analysis it is prove that there is a difference between the ratio of both the companies so 1st hypothesis is null hypothesis and 2nd hypothesis is working hypothesis.

Debt Equity Ratio

Yr.	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
TCS	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	-
Infosys	-	-	-	-	-

Interpretation:- This ratio judges the long-term financial position & soundness of the long term financial policies of the firm. The debt-equity ratio of both the companies is nil or (zero) which indicates that companies earnings will be sufficient to service the debt & also some free funds to take care of other business activities like-expansion, diversification, of business or starting a new venture.

H:- Here from the above analysis it is proved that 1st hypothesis is proved as working hypothesis because there is no difference between the ratio and 2nd is null hypothesis.

Asset turnover ratio

Yr.	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
TCS	1.49	2.45	2.48	2.85	3.18
Infosys	4.28	5.34	4.91	4.75	3.70

Interpretation:- Assets Turnover Ratio tells how successfully the company is using its assets to generate revenue. If a company can generate more sales with fewer assets it has a higher turnover ratio which tells it is a good company because it is using its assets efficiently & vice versa.

The above ratio indicates that TCS is better than Infosys because its asset turnover ratio is better than Infosys.

H:- 1st hypothesis is proved as null hypothesis and 2nd is working hypothesis because there is a difference between the ratio of both the companies.

Debtors Turnover Ratio

Yr.	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
TCS	6.54	7.19	5.59	4.77	5.04
Infosys	6.37	6.81	6.50	6.25	6.47

Interpretation:- This ratio shows that how quickly debtors are converted into cash & thus, indicates the efficiency of the staff entrusted with collection of amounts are from debtors. The above ratio data indicates that the debtors turnover ratio of TCS in 2011 is high after that it declines whereas the debtors turnover ratio of Infosys fluctuates steadily but debtors turnover ratio of Infosys is better than TCS.

H:- Above analysis proved that here 2nd hypothesis is working because the difference between both the companies are found.

Net Profit Ratio

Yr.	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
TCS	24.13	25.42	26.42	25.24	27.25
Infosys	26.36	24.28	25.60	23.38	21.72

Interpretation:- The Net profit ratio is an indicator of overall efficiency of the business. This ratio helps in determining the operational efficiency of the business. The net profit of TCS is tends to rise, whereas the net profit of Infosys declining. So, the overall efficiency of TCS is better than Infosys.

H:- there is a significant difference between the net profit ratio analysis so, here 1st hypothesis is null hypothesis and hence it is rejected and 2nd hypothesis is working hypothesis because there is a significant difference.

Interest Cover Ratio

Yr.	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
TCS	674.43	435.25	841.63	513.84	1006.74
Infosys	-	-	-	-	-

Interpretation:- The Interest Cover Ratio measures the ability of the co. to pay interest on its outstanding debt. Higher ICR indicate that a company can pay for its interest-expenses & vice versa (lower ratio 1.5:1). Interest cover ratio known as time interest earned.

H:- There is a significant difference between interest coverage ratio so 2nd hypothesis is proved as working hypothesis.

Earning Per Share

Yr.	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
TCS	28.62	38.62	55.97	65.23	94.17
Infosys	101.13	112.22	147.50	158.75	178.40

Interpretation:- This ratio helps in evaluating the prevailing market price of the share in the light of the profit-earning capacity the earning per share of Infosys in comparison with TCS is near to double which shows that the Infosys have the better performance & prospects.

H:- There is a difference between the ratio of both the companies that is why 2nd hypothesis is proved as working hypothesis.

Dividend Per Share

Yr.	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
TCS	20	14	25	22	32
Infosys	25	60	47	42	63

Interpretation:- This is to measure the dividend distributed per equity share. The above data make it clear that the dividend per share of Infosys is more than the TCS but fluctuations in both the companies are there.

H:- In this, the 1st hypothesis is null hypothesis and 2nd is working hypothesis because there is a difference between the ratio.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Both TCS and Infosys can improve their financial conditions by keeping in mind the following recommendations that are as follows:-

- 1- By improving their Current Ratio through:-
 - Faster conversion of debtors.
 - Pay off Current liabilities.
 - Sell off unproductive assets.
 - Improve current assets by raising shareholder's funds.
 - Sweep bank account.
- 2- By improving their Debt-Equity Ratio through:-
 - Increase profitable sales.
 - Watch inventory.
 - Restructure debt.
 - Sell assets and lease them back.
- 3- By improving their Assets turnover ratio through:-
 - Increase revenue.
 - Liquidate assets.
 - Leasing.
 - Improve efficiency.
 - Accelerate accounts receivables.
 - Better Inventory Management.

CONCLUSION

After making a study of the ratios, we come to conclude that:-

- Asset turnover ratio of TCS is better than Infosys.
- Debtors turnover ratio of Infosys is better than TCS.
- Net profit ratio of TCS is better than Infosys.
- Earning per share of Infosys is better than TCS.
- Dividend per share of Infosys is better than TCS.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The following are the some of the limitations of the study: the study takes into account only two companies such as TCS and Infosys. The study is limited to financial data for the period of 5 years from 2010-2014.

The financial data of both the companies are taken from the secondary source i.e..annual report of the companies. Qualitative aspects can also be included for the purpose of further study.

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